

Fully Homomorphic Encryption over an Artificial Neural Network

Robin Salen

Since the first conception of a computational model for Neural Networks in 1943, Artificial-Neural Networks have experienced in the past few years an incredible rise among artificial intelligence

algorithms. However, the knowledge within a neural network can be sensitive information that the owner may not want to share. In this purpose, we study the use of cryptography during the training

process of an artificial neural network. An encrypted neural network offers two beneficial properties: it can be released and trained in an unsecure environment, and it only makes encrypted predictions, with no influence on the outside world without decrypting the result. This project, entitled “Fully Homomorphic Encryption over an Artificial Neural Network”, follows the previous work from Ducas and Micciancio introducing a Fully Binary Homomorphic Encryption Scheme over lattices. From their scheme, we try to reduce the running time of a refresh procedure during the computation of a NAND binary gate by simultaneously evaluating multiple gates in one bootstrapping without decreasing the level of security. Applied with floating-point arithmetic and polynomial approximation for activation functions, we obtain an overall faster scheme for the purpose of deep learning methods.

While the global performance is improved, we are still facing the general drawback of Fully Homomorphic Encryption that is the running time of one bootstrapping procedure. We will dedicate

our future research to approximate arithmetic, in order to fasten up the refresh procedure while staying in the scope of accuracy of neural networks.

February 20, 2019